

**Towards a Programmable and Resilient
Orchestration Platform Bridging
Multi-Domain Networks**

Grand Challenge 10: Network and Service Orchestration Platform

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Abstract

This white paper presents the outcomes of the RESTART Grand Challenge 10, which focuses on the design of an advanced Network and Service Orchestration Platform. The proposed platform architecture follows the Service Based Management Architecture (SBMA) design principles defined by the 3GPP. It is modular and cloud-native, enabling orchestration across multi-domain, multi-technology environments. Further, it integrates domain-specific and cross-domain orchestrators, closed-loop automation mechanisms, AI/ML capabilities, and Network Digital Twins for dynamic resource and service management. The overall platform is designed to support end-to-end service lifecycle automation while maintaining flexibility and interoperability. Concrete implementations developed within RESTART are presented as examples of the functional entities composing the proposed architecture. Additionally, the white paper provides insights into the evolution of orchestration platforms towards 6G networks.

Keywords

5G/6G Networks, Network and Service Orchestration, Service-based Architecture, Algorithms, Network Digital Twins, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Standardization

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Contents

1	Introduction: Motivation, Problem Statement, and Overview	2
2	Limitation of Current Standards	3
2.1	O-RAN Alliance	6
2.2	TM Forum	7
2.2.1	ITU-T	9
2.3	ETSI ENI and ZSM	10
3	Management and Orchestration Architecture	11
4	Applicability and Examples	15
4.1	Network Intelligence	16
4.1.1	Network Digital Twins	16
4.1.2	Service Orchestration, AI-as-a-Service, and Closed Loops	19
4.1.3	Orchestration for Connected Healthcare on 6G Networks	21
4.2	Intra-domain Resource Management	23
4.2.1	Intelligent RAN Management	24
4.2.2	End-to-End Cross-Domain Network and Service Orchestration with LLMs	26
4.2.3	Intelligent Transport Network	28
4.2.4	ONOS/OpenROADM	33
4.2.5	ONOS/QKD	35
4.2.6	Mantra	36
4.2.7	Teraflow for Optical Networks	36
4.2.8	Model/ML-Based Hybrid Orchestration for Cloud-Native Network Functions	38
5	Future Directions Towards 6G	40
5.1	Architectural Evolution	41
5.2	Functional Advancements	42
5.2.1	Key Enabling Technologies	43
5.2.2	Reference Standards and Frameworks	44
6	Conclusions	45
7	References	46

1 Introduction: Motivation, Problem Statement, and Overview

The RESTART Grand Challenge 10 (GC10) has provided an overarching vision of Network and Service Orchestration (NSO), detailing the motivations and limitations of current approaches. Moreover, it has designed a comprehensive platform for advanced NSO, including architectural innovations that have been developed within the RESTART Program.

NSO is indeed critical in communications and computing infrastructures to enabling automated and dynamic management of network resources and services. It plays a crucial role in ensuring efficient deployment, scaling, and optimization of services across heterogeneous networks, including radio access networks (RANs) such as 5G/6G and Wi-Fi as well as software-defined optical and IP transport networks. It follows that NSO platforms need to be designed to manage complex, multi-domain, and multi-technology environments, while ensuring automated provisioning, configuration, and lifecycle management of network functions and services.

The orchestration process involves three main layers:

1. Service Orchestration, i.e., the automated deployment and management of network services, providing seamless integration across different network domains;
2. End-to-end (E2E) Resource Orchestration, i.e., the coordination of multiple network domains (e.g., core network, edge computing, radio interface), to provide end-to-end service automation;
3. Domain Orchestration, which focuses on managing physical and virtual network resources within a single domain, ensuring optimal allocation and utilization.

Several technologies contribute to the realization and effectiveness of NSO. First and foremost, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). The former separates the control and data planes and allows for centralized network management and programmability. The latter replaces or complements hardware-based network functions with virtual (i.e., software-based) network functions (VNFs), improving flexibility and scalability. Second, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) allow for predictive analytics, anomaly and failure detection, and automated decision-making in network management.

This document presents how, leveraging the above technologies, the RESTART Program

has designed a comprehensive Network and Service Orchestration Platform, including all the required functional blocks and interfaces. The platform architecture follows the Service Based Management Architecture (SBMA) design principles, as defined in (1) for network M&O in 3GPP networks. It thus looks at orchestration services as modular producers and consumers of management functions that interact through standardized APIs. These components include domain-specific orchestrators (e.g., for RAN, core, transport), cross-domain orchestrators (for E2E services and slices), resource monitoring and analytics services, and intelligence layers such as AI/ML-as-a-Service frameworks, closed-loop automation engines, and Network Digital Twin orchestration platforms. Exposure managers handle service and data discovery and access, ensuring interoperability and security in multi-tenant, multi-domain environments. For several functional blocks, the document then provides examples of how they have been developed within the RESTART Program, yielding an effective set of orchestration and management solutions.

Specifically, the rest of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses what current standards fail to provide and what will be needed in the future standards evolutions. Section 3 presents the Management and Orchestration (MANO) Architecture envisioned within the RESTART GC10. Section 4 then introduces the functional blocks that have been developed within the GC10, including Network Digital Twin (NDT) orchestration platforms, intelligence layers that exploit NDTs, such as AI/ML-as-a-Service frameworks and closed-loop automation engines, domain-specific orchestrators (e.g., for RAN, core, transport), cross-domain orchestrators (for E2E services and slices), as well as resource monitoring and analytics services. Finally, Section 5 envisions future directions that pave the way to the development of 6G network and computing systems, while Section 6 concludes the documents.

2 Limitation of Current Standards

This section describes the current Status of Network and Service Orchestration within the 3GPP Working Group (WG) SA5 (Management, Orchestration and Charging) and WG SA2 (System Architecture). As specified in these documents, which define the overall architecture for Management and Orchestration (MANO) and its interactions across network domains, the orchestration framework is primarily based on:

- Network Slice Orchestration (SA5, SA2):

- Managed by the Network Slice Management Function (NSMF) and Network Slice Subnet Management Function (NSSMF) to handle slice lifecycle management (instantiation, scaling, optimization)
- Defined within 3GPP TS 28.531 and TS 28.541, which describe slice management and its integration with 5G Core Network (5GC) and RAN;
- Service-Based Orchestration in 5GC (SA2, SA3):
 - In SA2, the Service-Based Architecture (SBA) enables dynamic service exposure and orchestration through the Network Repository Function (NRF), Policy Control Function (PCF), and Network Exposure Function (NEF)
 - SA3 (Security) ensures secure service orchestration via network exposure policies;
- Policy and Resource Orchestration (SA2, SA5):
 - In SA2, PCF provides QoS, traffic prioritization, and service policy enforcement, allowing dynamic adaptation to network demands
 - SA5 defines orchestration procedures for AI-driven and policy-based automation;
- Network Function Management (SA5):
 - The Network Function Management Function (NFMF) is responsible for lifecycle management of VNFs/CNFs across cloud and physical environments.

Orchestration in the 5G Core (5GC) Network. 3GPP has defined mature orchestration mechanisms for 5GC, based on the SBA principles (TS 23.501, TS 23.502). Key components include:

- NEF (SA2, SA6), which allows external applications to interact with network services via exposure APIs;
- NRF (SA2), managing service discovery and dynamic orchestration of network functions (NFs);
- PCF (SA2, SA5), controlling service-level policies and resource prioritization;
- AF (SA6), which enables application-driven service orchestration and policy control.

Although 5GC orchestration is well-defined, *its integration with transport networks, RAN orchestration, and multi-cloud environments remains an area for further development.*

Orchestration in the RAN Domain (SA2, RAN3). Unlike the 5GC, orchestration in the RAN domain is still evolving. Current 3GPP-defined mechanisms include:

- Functional Decomposition (SA2, RAN3): The introduction of the CU/DU/RU

split (TS 38.401, TS 38.470) enables more flexible deployment models. While these architectures allow for dynamic RAN deployments, orchestration mechanisms for CU/DU interactions remain relatively static in 3GPP.

- RAN Slice Management (SA5, RAN3): The integration of RAN slicing with NSMF/NSSMF allows for basic slice orchestration. However, dynamic RAN slicing and real-time traffic steering still require enhancements.

There is currently no standardized AI-driven RAN orchestration model in 3GPP, and automation capabilities remain limited compared to the 5GC domain.

Orchestration in Transport and Multi-Domain Networks (SA2, SA5, SA6).

Transport network orchestration is recognized but not fully addressed in 3GPP. Key points include:

- Transport Slice Coordination (SA5, SA2). 3GPP defines network slicing for 5GC and RAN, but transport slices are not natively orchestrated within 3GPP. Thus, operators must use external SDN/NFV orchestration (e.g., ETSI NFV MANO, ONAP, MEF LSO) for transport management.
- Fixed-Mobile Convergence (FMC) Orchestration (SA2, SA6). 3GPP does not yet provide a comprehensive orchestration framework for Fixed Broadband (FTTH, DSL, Cable) and Mobile Networks, limiting full end-to-end service management.

Current Limitations and Challenges.

- Limited Multi-Domain Orchestration: Orchestration in RAN, Core, and Transport is defined separately, with no unified multi-domain orchestration framework;
- Static RAN Orchestration: Unlike 5GC, RAN orchestration lacks dynamic resource scaling, AI-driven automation, and service exposure mechanisms;
- Fragmented Transport Orchestration: The lack of standardized transport slicing mechanisms limits the ability to orchestrate end-to-end network slices across RAN, Core, and Transport domains;
- Limited AI/ML-driven Automation: AI-driven closed-loop automation is not yet fully standardized within the 3GPP framework;
- Cloud-Native Integration Challenges: SBA-based orchestration lacks integration with external multi-cloud environments, hyperscalers, and Kubernetes-based orchestration models.

Future Evolution Areas and 3GPP Workgroups to Address the Above Gaps. To

enable end-to-end intelligent orchestration, 3GPP should focus on the following areas:

- Multi-Domain Orchestration (SA5, SA2): Define a unified orchestration model covering RAN, Core, Fixed Access, and Transport for seamless cross-domain automation;
- Dynamic RAN Orchestration (SA2, RAN3, SA5): Extend SBA-based orchestration to the RAN domain, integrating with real-time policy control mechanisms;
- Cross-Domain Network Slicing (SA2, SA5, SA6): Expand slice orchestration to include transport networks, edge computing, and fixed broadband;
- AI-Driven Closed-Loop Automation (SA5, SA6): Define AI/ML-driven orchestration frameworks to enable self-optimizing networks (SON), adaptive slicing, and predictive analytics;
- Cloud-Native Service Orchestration (SA6, SA5, SA2): Develop standards for managing SBA-based network functions in multi-cloud environments, including orchestrating microservices-based RAN and Core functions.

By addressing these challenges, 3GPP can evolve toward a fully converged, AI-driven, and intent-based orchestration framework, enabling zero-touch automation, end-to-end network slicing, and real-time adaptive service delivery for 5G Advanced, 6G, and beyond.

2.1 O-RAN Alliance

The O-RAN Alliance introduces a disaggregated and intelligent approach to 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) orchestration through the integration of three key components: the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, the Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC), and the Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC). These components collectively enhance the flexibility, efficiency, and automation of RAN operations, aligning with the broader goals of network softwarization and open interfaces.

Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), responsible for end-to-end management and orchestration of the RAN, ensuring seamless coordination between different network functions. It provides key functionalities such as:

- Lifecycle management of O-RAN components, including deployment, scaling, and updates.
- Configuration and policy management, enabling dynamic adaptation of network

parameters.

- Performance monitoring and assurance, leveraging data analytics to enhance network optimization.

By integrating AI/ML-driven insights, the SMO enables closed-loop automation, improving the adaptability and efficiency of RAN orchestration.

Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC), operating within a timeframe of 10 ms to 1 s, enabling real-time optimization of RAN behavior. Its primary functions include:

- Traffic steering and resource allocation, dynamically adjusting network resources to optimize performance.
- Interference management, mitigating issues such as spectrum congestion and cross-cell interference.
- QoS enforcement, ensuring optimal user experience based on network conditions and policies.

The Near-RT RIC interacts with RAN elements through open interfaces, executing xApps (real-time applications) that implement specific control and optimization functions.

Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC), operating at timescales beyond 1 s, focusing on predictive analytics, policy-based optimization, and AI-driven automation. Its key responsibilities include:

- Long-term optimization of RAN performance using historical data and predictive modeling.
- Policy management and orchestration, defining and enforcing control strategies for the Near-RT RIC.
- Training and deployment of AI/ML models, enabling intelligent automation of RAN functions.

2.2 TM Forum

The TM Forum provides a comprehensive framework for the orchestration and management of network and service operations. Its approach is built on well-established principles

such as the enhanced Telecom Operations Map (eTOM), the Open Digital Architecture (ODA), and the concept of Autonomous Networks (ANs). This document outlines TM Forum's orchestration methodology, its alignment with network operator organizational models, and the role of AI and NDTs in enabling next-generation networks.

eTOM and the Organization of Network Operators. The eTOM framework, a core component of TM Forum's standards, provides a structured view of a network operator's business processes. It defines the functions and interactions required for end-to-end service management and orchestration. eTOM is divided into three primary levels:

- **Strategy, Infrastructure Product (SIP):** Defines the strategic aspects of network operations, including long-term planning, product development, and investment strategies.
- **Operations:** Covers the management and assurance of network services, including fulfillment, assurance, and billing.
- **Enterprise Management:** Handles cross-functional activities such as finance, HR, and compliance.

Within the Operations layer, orchestration plays a crucial role in service fulfillment, ensuring that resources are dynamically allocated and managed based on real-time demands. The alignment of orchestration with eTOM ensures that process automation and service lifecycle management are well integrated into a network operator's structure.

Open Digital Architecture (ODA) and Orchestration. It is TM Forum's response to the increasing demand for cloud-native, agile, and interoperable service management. ODA replaces traditional monolithic OSS/BSS architectures with a modular, API-driven framework that allows for more dynamic and flexible orchestration. Key principles of ODA include:

- **Component-Based Design:** Services are orchestrated using independent, reusable components.
- **Standardized APIs:** Open APIs enable interoperability between different network and IT systems.
- **AI-Driven Automation:** AI enhances service orchestration by enabling predictive analytics and real-time decision-making.

Under ODA, orchestration is achieved through an intelligent orchestration layer that ensures seamless service lifecycle management. This layer interacts with various ODA

components, such as the Intelligent Operations Center (IOC) and AI-driven analytics engines, to enhance real-time decision-making.

Autonomous Networks and AI-Driven Orchestration. A critical evolution in network management is the move towards Autonomous Networks (ANs), where AI-driven orchestration plays a central role in automating operations across multiple network domains. TM Forum's AN framework defines different levels of autonomy, ranging from basic automation (Level 1) to fully autonomous, self-healing networks (Level 5). Key capabilities of AI-driven orchestration in this context include:

- **Self-Optimization:** AI dynamically adjusts network parameters based on traffic patterns and QoS requirements.
- **Self-Healing:** Predictive analytics enable proactive issue resolution before service degradation occurs.
- **Closed-Loop Automation:** Continuous monitoring and AI feedback loops ensure adaptive service orchestration.

The Role of NDTs in Orchestration. The introduction of NDTs provides a real-time, virtual representation of the network, enabling operators to simulate, predict, and optimize network behavior before implementing changes in the live environment. In the context of orchestration, TM Forum focuses on the following key aspects of NDTs:

- **Scenario Simulation:** Operators can test different orchestration strategies in a virtualized environment to improve decision-making and automation.
- **Impact Analysis:** Before applying policy changes, NDTs assess potential network-wide impacts, reducing risks and enhancing operational efficiency.

By integrating NDTs within its orchestration frameworks, TM Forum aims to enhance predictive analytics and decision automation, supporting more efficient and resilient network operations.

2.2.1 ITU-T

ITU-T has dealt with management and orchestration issues since the beginning, first for SDN networks then for 5G networks and is now exploring more innovative concepts such

as Intent based network and more in general to the role of AI. We can say that, compared to other standardization bodies, ITU-T remains at a higher level of abstraction. Related to IMT-2020 the Recommendation ITU-T Y.3111 (2017) was to provide network management and orchestration architecture and functional components for design, deployment and operation to implement network covering fixed and mobile networks. Subsequently, Recommendation ITU-T Y.3324 (2018) specified the high-level and functional requirements and architecture of autonomic management and control (AMC) for IMT-2020 networks. It also specifies interworking reference points between AMC and IMT-2020 management and orchestration architecture, and legacy NMS/OSS. More recently, the objective of Recommendation ITU-T Y.3159 (2023) is to specify a framework for classifying network slice levels in future networks. This framework is guidance for network slice deployment and management. A method for classifying network slice levels of future networks, including IMT-2020, is introduced. Related to novel network approaches, as for Intent-based networks, the recommendation Y.3161 describes management and orchestration for network slicing in IMT-2020 networks and beyond. In particular, it reports the architecture of intent-based network management and orchestration, detailing mechanisms and procedures.

2.3 ETSI ENI and ZSM

The European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI) has defined an architectural framework for the orchestration of NFV, named ETSI MANO, that allows for managing the lifecycle of VNFs (Virtual Network Functions), orchestrate virtualized network services, and control virtual infrastructure resources (NFVI). ETSI MANO thus allows for automatic operation of the network, however to arrive at a zero-touch behavior further interventions were necessary to analyze the behavior of the network in a dynamic regime with continuous changing and cyclical procedures and overall to take into account AI methods. ETSI has then also taken significant steps in embracing artificial AI/ML for an increased automation of network resource management and orchestration. Two prominent groups have been established: ETSI Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) (ETSI GS ENI 005 v2.1.1), and ETSI Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) (ETSI GS ZSM, vol. 2, 2019). ETSI ENI represents a centralized framework that delineates an AI-based approach to network management, by substantially adding intelligence on top of legacy systems, without necessitating substantial modifications. On the other hand, ETSI ZSM has already issued a reference architecture featuring distributed management and orchestration, including also closed-loop control, aiming at a deeper AI native approach.

The importance of ZSM is first of all the fact that it uses AI for its operation allowing a closed-loop automation from the collection and analysis of data that characterize the elements of the network and traffic. In this way, the network can react automatically in case of anomaly detection. Another fundamental aspect is that ZSM can operate on heterogeneous domains (e.g., access, transport, core, edge, slicing), and each domain manages a part of the network, including one or more ZSM Management Services.

3 Management and Orchestration Architecture

Modern networks require a **multi-layer, multi-domain orchestration architecture** to ensure seamless coordination across access, transport, and core layers. This approach enables **automated service provisioning, dynamic resource allocation, and cross-domain interoperability**.

The key features are as follows:

- **SBA:** Standardized APIs facilitate real-time interaction and flexible service composition;
- **AI-driven Automation:** Enables predictive analytics, intent-based provisioning, and closed-loop optimization;
- **Multi-layer Coordination:** Integrates physical, virtual, and cloud-native resources for end-to-end service delivery;
- **Federated Orchestration:** Ensures interoperability across different operators and service providers.

This architecture enhances **network efficiency, scalability, and resilience**, aligning with future **6G** requirements through intelligent automation and service-based principles. The high-level architecture proposed for the management and orchestration (M&O) system of future smart networks and services is represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Layered network orchestration architecture.

In more detail, Fig. 2 represents all the necessary building blocks inside a M&O

Figure 2: High-level functional architecture for the management and orchestration system of future mobile networks.

The architecture assumes the adoption of Service Based Management Architecture (SBMA) design principles, as defined in (1) for M&O in 3GPP networks. Following this approach, management and orchestration in mobile networks can be modeled through a set of cooperating management services as defined in the 3GPP and other reference SDOs. The M&O system architecture is structured as a composition of management services produced by management functions, i.e., logical entities (which may also be embedded in Network Functions) with the role of producer of one or more management services. The access to the capabilities offered by a management service provider towards external entities can be regulated according to exposure rules that may operate with per-tenant scope

and may be handled through a capability exposure governance. Fig. 2 assumes that all the proposed building blocks follow this structure, where each of them may produce and consume management services (Fig. 3) and multiple implementations of the same service can coexist over the same environment, all of them discoverable through a discovery service and, when exposed to external domains, with the related exposure rules managed through a capability exposure governance function. At this stage, the specific communication paradigm used for each service is out of the scope of this document.

Figure 3: M&O components acting as management service consumer and/or producer.

The M&O system operates over a multi-tenant virtualized environment realized over a distributed physical infrastructure with multiple domains spanning a computing continuum from the extreme edge to the cloud. The virtual environment hosts the access, core and transport domain, where for the transport domain multi-technology programmable networks are assumed. The representation in Fig. 2 identifies potential components of the M&O system, which are intended to collaborate together following the SBMA principles to implement the global logic of the network management. The various colours are representing different types of functionalities within the M&O system, as follows:

- Blue components represent orchestrators or controllers of specific domains (e.g., a management domain in the ETSI ZSM framework (2)). The following are identified:
 - Orchestrators of the RAN domain.
 - Orchestrators of the CN domain.
 - SDN controllers for the management of the transport network(s).
 - Resource orchestrator for computing resources related to provisioning of vertical or network applications in the continuum.
- Grey components represent M&O services with end-to-end (E2E) and cross-domain scope (e.g., an E2E service management domain in ETSI ZSM framework (2)). The following are identified:
 - Network Slice Management, including mechanisms for slice provisioning, lifecycle management and automation, with both end-to-end scope and per-subnet scope, interacting with the orchestrators of the respective domains;

- Continuum Resource Inventory and Network Topology, for discovery and management of computing nodes in the continuum and management of network topologies in the multi-technology transport domain(s);
 - Network and Compute Resource Monitoring and Data Analytics, implementing the management data analytics service and operating at different layers or domains, retrieving monitoring data and computing statistics related to physical infrastructure and computing resources, devices, network nodes in the transport domain or network functions, possibly interacting with other elements (e.g., NWDAF from the CN) or external data-sources.
 - End-to-end Cross-domain Service and Network Data Analytics, consuming the monitoring data from the previous service and generating analytical data with E2E scope, e.g., for end-to-end network slices, services, etc.
 - End-to-end Cross-domain Network Orchestrator, implementing the procedures for end-to-end orchestration at the network level, including mechanisms for provisioning, lifecycle management and automation, e.g., for self-recovery, self-configuration, self-optimization.
 - End-to-end Cross-domain Service Orchestrator, implementing the procedures for end-to-end orchestration (as before) but operating at the service level. It should be noted that both network and service orchestration may operate based on a prescriptive (rule-based or policy-based) or intent-based approach. Depending on the adopted approach, different kinds of interfaces, internal functionalities and modules would be needed.
- Green components represent added-value network intelligence services, with intra-domain or cross-domain scope, which can be consumed transversally by the other M&O services to adopt specialized technologies, processes, algorithms or techniques (which can be provided as alternatives by multiple vendors) to implement their logic. Example of functionalities which can be provided by these services, potentially even as result of a joint collaboration, include e.g., autonomous self-healing and self-optimization, optimized function placement, ML-based predictions, traffic deep inspection for transport path optimization, etc. It is important to note that all these services may be provided in an on-demand mode (e.g., through a related Governance function), so that their respective management functions can be deployed, distributed and customized according to the specific needs of the consumer, but always consumable through a common interface to guarantee multi-vendor compatibility and interoperability. The following services are proposed:
 - AI/ML-as-a-Service Framework, for provisioning and management of AI/ML functions or ML models in support of service or network orchestration, across all the stages of the ML model lifecycle ((3)).

Figure 4: Operator Platform roles and interfaces reference architecture (9).

- Closed Loops (CL) Framework, for provisioning, governance, monitoring and coordination of closed control loops for service and/or network automation ((4; 5)).
- Network Digital Twins (NDT) Framework, for provisioning, governance, monitoring and coordination of NDTs to model various concurrent aspects of network characteristics and behaviour and to preliminarily assess the impact of network (re-)configuration actions in a protected sandbox ((6; 7)).
- Orange components represent generalized services which are needed as part of the SBMA to enable a proper interaction and collaboration among the available services. In particular, the Service Exposure Manager handles the registration and discovery of available services, also regulating the exposure of the services within the organization, while the Data Exposure Manager performs a similar role but for the exchange of data to be shared among the services.
- The Capabilities Exposure component deals with the governance of the M&O services exposure towards external administrative domains or entities, e.g., towards verticals or other MNOs (similar to the Exposure Governance Management Function – EGMF – mentioned in (8)). In the particular case of cross-operator federation, additional architectural elements may be introduced, e.g., a Federation Manager and a Federation Broker, as defined in (9; 10).

4 Applicability and Examples

The sections below presents concrete solutions that have been developed within RESTART and that implement some of the functional blocks composing the proposed platform architecture.

4.1 Network Intelligence

This section offers insights into the transformation of 5G and 6G mobile networks through the integration of advanced technologies such as NDTs, service orchestration, and automated management. Specifically, Section 4.1.1 delves into the pivotal role of NDTs in enhancing network automation, reducing operational costs, and streamlining the management of complex modern network infrastructures. The COHERENT project and its subproject VOLTA propose a cloud-native framework to integrate NDTs with network management systems, thereby improving the validation of automated decisions and runtime operations. Section 4.1.2, dedicated to WatchEDGE, outlines a hierarchical approach to service orchestration across multiple administrative sites, leveraging AI-as-a-Service and closed loops to optimize resource management and ensure privacy in advanced AI services. Lastly, Section 4.1.3, related to the 6G SALUS project, addresses the application of 6G networks in the healthcare sector, with a focus on differentiated QoS required to support critical applications such as telemedicine and emergency response. By employing ML techniques, the 6G SALUS architecture anticipates and dynamically manages traffic, enhancing the continuity and reliability of healthcare services. This section thus outlines a complex and innovative framework for the evolution of mobile network management, promoting efficiency, security, and reliability through emerging technologies.

4.1.1 Network Digital Twins

The adoption of NDTs is a key enabler to introduce full automation in the management and orchestration of 5G/6G mobile networks, specifically helping runtime operations such as performance management, fault management, and predictive maintenance. While 5G/6G networks and infrastructures are becoming more and more complex, in terms of heterogeneity, density and performance demands, the introduction of NDTs (together with complementary enablers such as AI/ML), can significantly help in reducing the OPEX and thus the burden of managing and operating highly concurrent services and applications. Relevant standard organizations, such as 3GPP, ETSI ZSM and Internet Research Task Force (IRTF) have already started to tackle NDTs. However, most of the current standardization activities are still at their early stages, focusing on investigating use cases and requirements related to the adoption of NDTs, specifically targeting their use in support of 5G/6G network and service management.

Based on this preliminary work, the COHERENT project, together with its cascade call project VOLTA, defines a cloud-native NDT framework that integrates with 5G/6G network and service management systems and platforms to provide innovative functionality to the management and orchestration logics of network services, slices and resources, such as: i) testing and validation of the effects of reconfiguration and optimization actions implemented at the service or network slice level, ii) testing and validation of decisions made by zero-touch network and service automation solutions (e.g., based on AI-driven ETSI ZSM closed loops), iii) in general, testing and validation in sandbox mode.

Having as key goal the integration of NDTs with 5G/6G network and service management platform to further improve and enhance automation capabilities, COHERENT and VOLTA propose an NDT management and orchestration framework to properly manage and operate tailored NDT instances that model in the digital world the behavior and characteristics of a set of interconnected network nodes, assets and components. Indeed, digital twin management, control and optimization is the key to achieve efficient deployment and value of NDTs in 5G/6G networks and systems. The intended consumers of such NDT management and orchestration framework include: i) closed loop frameworks, and in particular multi-layer closed loops acting at different levels (service, network, computing resources), that can use NDT instances to validate, refine and optimize the reliability of their (AI-driven) zero-touch automation mechanisms, ii) management and orchestration services that include (or consume) automation mechanisms (such as those indicated in grey in the Fig. 2) to validate the effects and behaviors of specific network and service planning strategies, and runtime optimization actions.

Fig. 5 shows a high-level architecture of the NDT Management and Orchestration framework proposed by COHERENT and VOLTA. NDT instances are assumed to expose a set of APIs to: i) enable setup, configuration and monitoring of the specific digital twin assets and NDT instances, ii) receive actions and commands from NDT consumers, to trigger specific conditions or behaviors, and retrieve their effect and results in the digital twin, iii) collect real-time data from physical assets (or other NDT instances) and align the digital twin status.

COHERENT and VOLTA adopt a cloud-native approach, using KubeEdge as reference solution for the implementation of the NDT framework and the execution of the NDT instances based on AAS. For this, the Platform manager interfaces with this Kubernetes enabled underlying compute continuum infrastructure for (spanning from far-edge to edge and cloud) to deploy the various digital twin assets required to realize tailored NDT instances. The DT Manager in Fig. 5 covers the management of multiple digital twin

instances, including the creation, configuration and deletion of digital twin instances, taking care to manage the required resources to execute the given digital twin instances. COHERENT adopts the Asset Administrative Shell (AAS) as the reference digital twin modelling solution, therefore the DT Manager supports the operations required to manage AAS instances tailored to the specific NDT needs, including setup and deployment through the related AAS APIs. The DT Manager takes also care to coordinate the interactions among interdependent NDT instances, which may be created to replicate complex multi-domain and multi-layer scenarios.

Figure 5: High-level architecture of COHERENT and VOLTA NDT Orchestration platform.

The Platform Orchestration and Optimization allows to manage and orchestrate complex digital twin instances, composed of multiple digital twin assets. It coordinates the deployment and operation of interconnected digital twin components to realize NDT instances tailored to the given user or consumer needs, as shown in Fig. 6. The Platform Orchestration and Optimization also covers the digital twin assets and instance placement aspects, providing resource allocation mechanisms capable of satisfying deployment constraints that can vary according to the specific NDT scenario. In addition, it supports digital twin assets and instances monitoring capabilities, enabling collection of data from the compute continuum infrastructure where the NDT instances are executed (e.g. KubeEdge and Kubernetes) related to resource usage (such as CPU, memory, etc.) as well as power consumption (e.g. leveraging on solutions like Kepler).

Figure 6: NDT instances deployment in multi-cluster Kubernetes environments.

4.1.2 Service Orchestration, AI-as-a-Service, and Closed Loops

The RESTART WatchEDGE project focuses on the management of services across multiple administrative sites, called islands, handled through a hierarchy of orchestrators. In particular, the orchestration solution relies on local orchestrators residing one per island coordinated by a central entity called Platform orchestrator, responsible for the E2E service orchestration and management. Fig. 7 shows the architecture of the orchestration solution. It can be noted that the Platform Orchestrator is actually a logical component which encompasses a number of orchestrators for the management of i) E2E services, ii) public/private cloud resources, and iii) network and service automation, along with modules for resource allocation and edge site inventorying.

Figure 7: WatchEDGE hierarchical orchestration high-level architecture with main interactions.

The E2E SO decomposes the service in sub-components and selects per each one the target environment i.e., edge site (CS) or cloud, along with the specific WAN working as transport network between them. In this task, the E2E SE is supported by the Multi-Site Inventory, a repository maintaining the details of CSs, Public/Private Clouds, and WANs and by the Resource Allocation (RA) module. The RA collects information related to resource availability on the CSs and, where possible, from public/private clouds and provides the logic to allocating resources for the E2E service, including the selection of a proper WAN. The E2E SO then can request to the target CS Orchestrator and the SD-WAN orchestrator i) the provision of the edge component of the E2E service and ii) the configuration of the target WAN, respectively. To provision on the cloud the centralized components of the E2E service, the E2E SO makes a request to the Cloud Resource Orchestrator CRO, which performs the orchestration exploiting the interface exposed by the target cloud platform. The CL (Closed-Loop) Management functions are in charge of managing the so-called closed-loops, the entities designed to enable service and resource management automation. The stages of the loop (typically Monitoring, Analysis, Decision, and Execution) are realised as microservices and the CL itself is a cloud application completely orchestral and configurable. The CL deployment is requested by the E2E SO and realized through the CRO, for the E2E layer automation and by the CS Orchestrator for the Edge layer automation. The edge sites are characterized by multiple network and computational capabilities and offer XaaS functionalities e.g., FaaS and AIaaS. In particular, by exploiting the multiplicity of the edge site in combination

with the public cloud, it is possible to provide advanced privacy-preserving AI services based on Federated Learning techniques. In this regard, the orchestration facility properly configures the different cloud environments and acts on the SD-WAN orchestrator to guarantee adequate network resources for the exchange of large amounts of data and AI/ML models from the edge to the central site and vice versa.

4.1.3 Orchestration for Connected Healthcare on 6G Networks

In the connected healthcare context, explored and demonstrated by the RESTART 6G SALUS project, the integration of applications and devices with advanced communication networks is critical for the delivery of high-quality medical services. Applications such as remote patient monitoring, telemedicine, and emergency response systems rely heavily on the network's ability to provide reliable, high-speed, and low-latency communication.

Differentiated QoS becomes essential in these contexts to ensure that mission-critical healthcare data is prioritized appropriately. Specifically, the network must differentiate between different types of services and allocate resources accordingly. Critical Services, like remote surgery, emergency response coordination, and life-support monitoring require the highest QoS with ultra-low latency and high reliability. Non-critical Services, like patient record updates or appointment scheduling can operate with standard QoS levels. This differentiation is facilitated using 5G QoS Identifiers (5QI) in 5G networks. These identifiers help categorize and manage traffic types based on performance and priority, ensuring that critical healthcare data is prioritized over less critical traffic. Traditionally, networks have prioritized emergency services by dedicating resources and pre-empting other traffic. However, as we look to the future, a diverse array of mission-critical and business-critical services—including potentially high-volume, mass-market applications—will require simultaneous guarantees alongside non-critical services. These services must maintain appropriate QoS under all conditions, even during emergencies, making simple pre-emption insufficient. To minimize the impact on other services when provisioning critical ones like eHealth, it is essential to employ advanced traffic engineering techniques. These techniques should dynamically assign network paths based on real-time network conditions, anticipated incoming services, and the ability of existing services to be rerouted without degrading quality. Furthermore, networks must continuously optimize load distribution to ensure resource availability for all services. By adapting to changing network conditions, they can enhance performance and resource utilization, maintaining

readiness for unexpected events or surges in demand. This necessitates leveraging AI technologies to forecast service demands and optimize configurations [Iovanna et al., “*Intent-based AI system in packet-optical networks towards 6G. IEEE, Journal of Optical Communication, Volume: 16 Issue: 7*”]. Such approaches improve the capacity to perform dynamic network operations—like proactive rerouting—while considering node configuration times to ensure traffic continuity and prevent instability. Additionally, some services will operate on private dedicated networks, while others will be delivered over public networks, where ensuring service availability under any circumstances presents significant challenges.

In relation to the “High-level functional architecture for the management and orchestration system of future mobile networks” of GC10, depicted in Fig.1 of this document, 6G SALUS contributes to **three building blocks** (one in the green part and two in the grey part).

ML-based service, traffic, and load prediction(Green block). The 6G SALUS architecture uses ML techniques to predict traffic from mobile networks to transport networks, which is crucial for managing healthcare data traffic’s unpredictable nature. Healthcare applications often generate variable traffic, such as spikes during emergencies or increased patient monitoring. ML algorithms analyse historical and real-time data to forecast these traffic fluctuations, allowing the network to proactively allocate resources. This ensures that healthcare-specific service level agreements (SLAs) related to performance metrics like throughput, latency, and packet loss are met. By predicting traffic changes, the network can maintain the desired QoS by adjusting resources before congestion occurs, optimizing the transport network to prioritize high-priority healthcare data with necessary bandwidth and low latency.

E2E Cross-domain Network Orchestrator (Inc. Automation) (Grey block). The second building block where 6G SALUS contributes focuses on the automatic mapping of services with different QoS requirements across various network domains, radio access and core, and transport. Healthcare services often have diverse QoS requirements. For example, life-critical diagnostic data in emergency demands ultra-reliable low-latency communication. The orchestration component automatically maps each service to the appropriate network resources across the layers that can fulfill these QoS needs. Additionally, emergency healthcare services might need to be deployed rapidly in specific geographical areas affected by an accident or by a disaster. The orchestration system can automatically establish high-priority network services with the necessary QoS across affected regions involving the entire radio-transport-cloud chain.

E2E Network Slice (Grey block). 6G SALUS also considers E2E network slice activation and assurance, provisioned with guaranteed QoS metrics, isolating critical medical data from other network traffic. The investigated solution automates the linkage between the RAN and core network slices with the appropriate transport network slice. This integration ensures that QoS is maintained consistently across all segments of the network. This block is linked with the mentioned predictive capabilities from the ML-based service, traffic, and prediction block, so that the network can ensure that the transport segment meets the necessary SLAs for healthcare services. This synergy between the green and grey blocks enhances the overall reliability and performance.

4.2 Intra-domain Resource Management

This section focuses on the crucial aspect of intra-domain resource management, detailing strategies and mechanisms employed within specific network segments to optimize performance, efficiency, and service delivery. It presents several key approaches investigated within different research projects. These include: intelligent RAN management leveraging AI, intents, and O-RAN concepts within the RESTART SUPER project, as explored in Section 4.2.1; the emerging use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for automating end-to-end orchestration tasks and translating intents, discussed in Section 4.2.2; advanced orchestration techniques for transport networks developed in SUPER, encompassing NFV orchestration across backbone, access, and RAN domains, with a specific focus on managing distributed in-network Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) using programmable data planes, detailed in Section 4.2.3. Furthermore, the section covers various methods for optical resource management explored in RIGOLETTO, such as using the ONOS SDN controller for classical optical networks based on OpenROADM (Section 4.2.4) and extending it for Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) device control (Section 4.2.5), alongside the TIP MANTRA approach for controlling IPoWDM nodes (Section 4.2.6), and the extension of TeraFlow in the optical domain. Finally, it presents the ADAPTO project's hybrid model-based and machine learning-driven methods for orchestrating cloud-native functions across distributed cloud-edge infrastructures (Section 4.2.8). Thus, the section overall explores the architectures, standards (e.g., 3GPP, O-RAN, ETSI, OpenROADM, OpenConfig, TIP MANTRA, TeraFlow), and specific technologies enabling sophisticated resource control within individual network domains.

4.2.1 Intelligent RAN Management

To support dynamic service requirements, efficient resource utilization, and advanced RAN optimization in 5G and beyond networks, the SUPER project proposes a dedicated intradomain management and orchestration architecture for the RAN segment. The proposed solution enables intent-driven, standards-compliant control of RAN services, integrating AI-assisted management functions to address key use cases such as energy saving and service lifecycle optimization. The high-level architecture proposed for the intradomain resource M&O of the RAN segment is represented in Fig. 8. This section highlights the standard specifications driving the design as well as the description of the functionalities of each of the represented components and the mapping onto the high-level functional architecture for the management and orchestration system of future mobile networks represented in Fig. 2.

Figure 8: RAN intra-domain resource and orchestration architecture in SUPER project.

The proposed architecture has been designed according to 3GPP Technical Report (TR) 28.801 on the management and the orchestration of network slicing for next-generation networks.

The Service Orchestrator in Continuum of Cloud and Edge Resources (SOCCER) acts as Communication Service Management Function (CSMF) and can be mapped onto the “End-to-end Cross-domain Service Orchestrator” in Fig. 1. In fact, this component is

responsible for the management of Vertical Services (VS) deployed over end-to-end 5G network slices (NS). In this regard, SOCCER is capable of translating high-level service requirements into NS characteristics to be requested by consuming the services provided by the Network Slice Management Function (NSMF). In particular, it interacts with the NS Template Catalog to retrieve an NS model to satisfy the service requirements and with the MOI Generic Management Service API to create NetworkSliceController object and trigger NS instance provisioning according to 3GPP TS 28.532.

The NSMF component can be mapped onto the “End-to-end Cross domain Network orchestrator” in Fig. 1. This component is responsible for the modeling of the NSs, according to GSMA Network Slice Template (NEST) and 3GPP Network Slice Template (NST) models, as well as for the LifeCycle Management (LCM) of the end-to-end NS and the related Network Slice Subnets (NSS). To achieve this, the NSMF is in charge of computing the resource arbitration and allocation and NSS coordination by interacting with network segment specific Network Slice Subnet Management Functions (NSSMFs). In the context of the SUPER project, the NSMF consumes the MOI and the Subscription Generic Management Service APIs (3GPP TS 28.532) to create a NetworkSliceSubnetController object to trigger the NSS instance provisioning and to receive notifications on NSS instance LCM events, respectively.

The RAN NSSMF (RAN-NSSMF) processes the on-demand RAN NSS provisioning and (re)configuration requests coming from the NSMF by interacting with specific network segment controllers operating on the respective domain resources. In the context of the SUPER project, the RAN-NSSMF consumes the Intent Driven Management API defined in 3GPP TS 28.532 and exposed by the RAN Service Management and Orchestration platform (SMO). The SMO acts as an "intent handler", capable to translate declarative service requests into imperative commands for the dedicated RAN Management functions. O-RAN compliant SMO Intents-driven Management is implemented according to the ORAN WG1 dedicated Technical Report (TR).

The SMO is responsible for mapping all supported intents, related to exposed RAN capabilities, into domain-specific workflows, generally by the activation of RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) services. These services are implemented by so-called rApp, which are instantiated in the non-real-time RIC hosted in the SMO platform. For the specific purpose of this work, the Intent-Management capability of the deployed SMO is dedicated to a single example of rApp based on OREO.

OREO (11; 12) is an O-RAN RIC rApp orchestrator designed to maximize the number of RAN services (xApps) running concurrently within the near-real-time RIC. OREO's

key idea is that RAN services are a composition of xApps, which can be shared among different services whenever they operate to perform semantically equivalent functions, and the xApp output is of sufficient quality to fulfill the service requirements. OREO implements an algorithmic solution that selects the best service configuration, maximizes the number of shared xApps, and dynamically allocates their resources. This integration targets SUPER project Use Case (UC) 01, “Energy Saving application by O-RAN RIC”, and UC 08, “Optimization LifeCycle using O-RAN non-Real Time Control loop”, for this reason, the intent D5 and D9 intent examples reported in ANNEX D of 3GPP TS 28.312 have been taken as a reference starting point.

4.2.2 End-to-End Cross-Domain Network and Service Orchestration with LLMs

The integration of LLMs into E2E cross-domain network and service orchestration signifies a pivotal advancement in automating network operations. By harnessing LLMs, it’s feasible to interpret high-level service intents articulated in natural language and convert them into executable orchestration actions, thereby enhancing the efficiency and adaptability of network management systems (13).

A notable application of LLM-driven orchestration involves the collaboration between robotic systems and optical transport networks (OTNs). In this context, multiple LLM-empowered agents interact across domains to perform tasks such as real-time topology retrieval, network optimization using physical models, and robotic fiber switching. These agents utilize function calling to access domain-specific tools and data, enabling them to retrieve network parameters, analyze Quality of Transmission (QoT), and plan collision-free robotic movements (14).

The orchestration framework assigns specific roles to intelligent agents within each domain. For instance, in the OTN domain, agents might evaluate the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) of various paths based on real-time network data, determine optimal routing, and communicate these decisions to the robotic domain. Conversely, in the robotic domain, agents receive network optimization results and execute corresponding physical actions, such as adjusting fiber connections, to maintain optimal network performance (14).

Implementing LLMs in cross-domain orchestration also addresses challenges associated with network slicing management. LLMs can translate user intents into technical requirements,

Figure 9: Direct Prompting VS CoC Prompting. Even if the same LLM is employed, the Python code produced by the LLM is more effective in performing the task in place of directly querying the LLM.

map network functions to the appropriate infrastructure, and oversee the entire lifecycle of network slices. This capability is particularly beneficial in environments involving multiple administrative domains, where seamless coordination is essential for maintaining service quality (15).

Moreover, integrating LLMs with continual reinforcement learning has been proposed to enhance autonomous network orchestration. This approach leverages LLMs for high-level planning and reinforcement learning agents for low-level decision-making, aiming to achieve efficiency, accuracy, and adaptability in complex network environments (16).

Finally, LLMs have been effectively utilized for analyzing log files and extracting valuable knowledge from them. A notable example is the work in (17), where they applied LLMs to process networking log files, demonstrating the potential of these models in knowledge extraction tasks. As shown in the Fig. 9, it has been found that asking the model for generating source code for log analysis, is more effective than directly prompting the LLM.

4.2.3 Intelligent Transport Network

The evolution of modern networks necessitates a transport infrastructure that can dynamically adapt to the stringent requirements of emerging applications, particularly those leveraging AI-driven workloads. At the core of this transformation is a NFV orchestrator capable of concurrently managing both virtualized network functions and computing services. This dual orchestration capability ensures seamless integration between AI-driven applications and transport networks spanning backbone, access, and radio access domains.

In backbone networks, the NFV orchestrator optimizes IP transport services by dynamically provisioning virtual routers, traffic engineering policies, and service function chaining to enhance end-to-end performance. It enables intent-based networking, adjusting transport paths based on real-time traffic patterns, quality-of-service requirements, and energy efficiency constraints.

In access networks, the orchestrator manages virtualized edge resources, facilitating the deployment of AI-driven applications closer to the end user. By dynamically scaling network slices and virtualized broadband network gateways, it ensures low-latency, high-reliability connectivity, essential for applications such as autonomous systems and industrial automation.

In RANs, the NFV orchestrator plays a crucial role in optimizing virtualized RAN components, orchestrating radio resource allocation in coordination with transport network policies. This allows for the efficient coexistence of multiple service types, from enhanced mobile broadband to ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), ensuring optimal spectrum utilization and seamless AI-driven automation.

By integrating network intelligence with service orchestration, this NFV-enabled transport network framework provides a foundation for scalable, high-performance connectivity tailored to the demands of AI workloads. It enables a paradigm shift from static transport configurations to adaptive, intent-driven network orchestration, unlocking new opportunities in next-generation digital services.

Orchestration of In-Network Intrusion Detection System (IDS) with Data Plane Programmability and In-Network Computing. The increasing complexity of network security threats necessitates advanced detection and mitigation mechanisms that can operate at line

rate with minimal overhead. Traditional IDSs often struggle to keep pace with high-speed traffic and dynamically evolving attack vectors. To address these limitations, modern architectures leverage Data Plane Programmability and In-Network Computing (INC) to deploy IDS functionalities directly within the network fabric. The NFV orchestrator plays a crucial role in managing and optimizing these distributed security functions.

By leveraging programmable data planes based on P4 and eBPF, the orchestrator dynamically instantiates and configures in-network IDS components at strategic points in the network, including backbone, access, and radio access networks. This enables real-time traffic inspection, anomaly detection, and threat mitigation without diverting packets to external security appliances. The orchestrator coordinates updates to match-action tables, packet parsing logic, and flow-level analytics, ensuring that the IDS remains responsive to emerging threats.

In-network computing further enhances IDS efficiency by offloading packet analysis tasks to network devices with specialized processing capabilities, such as SmartNICs and programmable switches. The NFV orchestrator intelligently distributes IDS workloads across available network resources, balancing performance and computational overhead. Through intent-based policies, it dynamically adjusts the level of inspection based on network conditions, threat intelligence feeds, and service-level agreements.

Additionally, the orchestrator ensures seamless integration of in-network IDS with broader security frameworks, enabling automated response mechanisms such as flow redirection, traffic rate limiting, and dynamic firewall rule updates. This approach significantly reduces detection latency while enhancing the scalability and resilience of security operations.

Effective deployment of a distributed IDS requires intelligent orchestration of VNFs with learning capabilities (so called WL-VNFs and defined in the remainder of this Section) across multiple network domains, including backbone, access, and radio access networks. The NFV orchestrator plays a central role in this process by:

- Dynamically instantiating, scaling, and migrating WL-VNFs based on real-time traffic analysis and threat intelligence.
- Optimizing placement of WL-VNFs to balance network load, minimize detection overhead, and increasing the probability of threat detection.
- Enforcing security policies by adapting IDS configurations in response to detected threats.
- Coordinating communication between WL-VNFs to form a cooperative, distributed

intrusion detection mechanism.

By leveraging NFV orchestration, data plane programmability, and in-network computing, this approach transforms IDS into an adaptive, high-performance security framework that enables proactive threat detection and mitigation with minimal impact on network performance, representing a paradigm shift in network security.

The overall architecture of the distributed in-network IDS is illustrated in Fig. 10, which highlights the role of the NFV orchestrator in managing IDS functions across different network layers.

Figure 10: Architecture of the distributed in-network IDS leveraging data plane programmability and in-network computing.

At the core of the distributed IDS is the concept of a Weak Learner (WL), a lightweight model that makes limited but statistically significant decisions on traffic anomalies. Unlike monolithic IDS approaches, which rely on centralized and complex classifiers, WLS operate as independent detection units, each trained to recognize specific traffic patterns, anomalies, or attack signatures. While a single weak learner may have limited detection accuracy, combining multiple weak learners into an ensemble model – which is denoted as Strong Learner (SL) – significantly improves overall detection performance. Weak learners are well-suited for in-network IDS due to their small computational footprint, making them deployable within programmable data plane devices. These models perform low-latency feature extraction and classification on network packets in real time, enabling early-stage threat detection before forwarding traffic to deeper inspection layers.

To integrate weak learners into a distributed IDS framework, each weak learner is encapsulated

sulated as a VNF, referred to as a Weak Learner VNF (WL-VNF). This encapsulation enables flexible deployment, scaling, and orchestration of detection functions across the network. The NFV orchestrator dynamically instantiates WL-VNFs based on traffic load, security policies, and detected anomaly trends. Each WL-VNF operates as a lightweight virtualized function that inspects traffic in real time, classifying packets based on pre-defined attack signatures or statistical models. By treating weak learners as VNFs, the IDS architecture benefits from dynamic provisioning and migration, ensuring optimal placement of security functions across the infrastructure.

A single weak learner may lack the capability to comprehensively detect complex attack patterns. To overcome this limitation, multiple WL-VNFs are chained together to form an ensemble model. Each WL-VNF focuses on a specific subset of traffic features, leveraging different detection methodologies such as anomaly-based, signature-based, or machine learning-driven classification. The NFV orchestrator coordinates the chaining process, dynamically linking WL-VNFs based on evolving security threats. This ensemble approach enhances detection accuracy while maintaining low-latency processing, as each WL-VNF contributes partial insights that, when aggregated, provide a comprehensive security assessment.

To achieve real-time IDS functionality, WL-VNFs are deployed on programmable data plane (PDP) devices such as P4 switches, SmartNICs, and eBPF-enabled network interfaces. These devices provide high-speed, hardware-accelerated packet processing capabilities, allowing WL-VNFs to inspect and classify packets directly within the forwarding path. The NFV orchestrator manages the deployment of WL-VNFs across PDP devices, ensuring optimal resource utilization and adapting to changing network conditions. This approach eliminates the need for centralized deep packet inspection (DPI) engines, reducing detection latency and improving scalability.

Extending SOCCER Orchestrator to Support Distributed IDS for Programmable Networks.

In the context of the SUPER project, the logic of the SOCCER has been extended to support the provisioning of network service components over programmable data plane devices, such as P4 switches, SmartNICs, and eBPF-enabled interfaces. SOCCER has been originally designed and developed to provide capabilities to model vertical services in the form of intents, i.e., Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), and to manage their life cycle operations such as provisioning, (re)configuration and termination. The application components taken into consideration are deployed over the continuum resources in the form of cloud-native components. By integrating capabilities for managing WL-VNFs

deployment over programmable data plane devices, the capabilities of SOCCER have been enhanced towards a comprehensive management of scalable and distributed services, capable of performing in-network packet inspection and anomaly detection at multiple distributed points in the network. In particular, SOCCER has been extended to support LCM operations on the IDS architecture described in the previous section, providing capabilities for provisioning, scaling, and migration of the IDS functions in response to real-time network conditions and threat intelligence. These new functionalities leverage intent-based policies, to enforce effective and efficient security while trying to minimize processing overhead and latency.

The extended SOCCER architecture for distributed IDS deployment is illustrated in Fig. 11.

Figure 11: Extended SOCCER architecture to support application components deployment over programmable data plane devices.

SOCCER service orchestration logic has been extended to support dynamic service decomposition and to delegate LCM operations for specific application components to external domain-specific orchestrators. To implement this delegation mechanism, the VSB information model and the service LCM logic have been extended. In particular, the original VSB information model has been extended to provide specifications on which application components have to be deployed using the original SOCCER NFV orchestration framework and which ones have to be delegated to external domain-specific orchestrators. In the context of the Distributed IDS (D-IDS) service developed within the SUPER project, the LCM operations on the IDS components running on high-speed programmable data plane devices have been delegated to the so-called Programmable Data Plane Orchestrator (PDPO), enabling LCM and monitoring of services spanning across multiple domains with heterogeneous control mechanisms. For this purpose, a new

PDPO driver has been implemented to interact with the PDPO to request provisioning, (re)configuration and termination of application components over programmable data plane devices and to retrieve the status of the active deployment instances.

These enhancements enable multi-domain orchestration for coordinating NFV-based IDS deployments with in-network security enforcement mechanisms, allowing for low-latency, high-speed intrusion detection ensuring orchestration scalability across complex network environments without compromising network performance.

4.2.4 ONOS/OpenROADM

The Open Network Operating System (ONOS) SDN open-source project provides a broad and reliable environment that enables the programmability of packet networks (e.g., networks composed of layer-2 switches configured using the OpenFlow protocol) (18). RIGOLETTO proposes using the ONOS platform to control optical networks for both traditional communications and quantum key distribution.

In the context of traditional communication the main roles of the optical controller are: (i) retrieve devices description from data plane and abstract them toward the upper control layers (e.g., the network orchestrator and the digital twin); (ii) receive the service configuration requests by the upper control layers and translate them in a set of data plane configuration messages.

The ONOS version available at the RIGOLETTO starting time was already providing a rich north-bound interface (NBI) based on REST APIs and, on its south-bound interface (SBI), it was able to connect a variety of packet and optical devices (e.g., exploiting NETCONF protocol). In addition, the ONOS core already implements basic connectivity services using the concept of intent that simplify and automate service management (e.g., in case of network failure) (19).

Considerable development effort within the ONOS controller has been performed at several levels: in the NBI, in the SBI and in the Core for introducing the new features required to integrate the controller in the RIGOLETTO context such as: (i) enable integration with orchestrator and digital twin (NBI); (ii) develop drivers toward new devices and update existing drivers against the most recent versions of standard models (SBI); (iii) introduce

the support of flexible-grid and multi-band (NBI, core, SBI); (iv) activate intents using as end-points the ROADMs's ports (core).

More specifically, within the RIGOLETTO project, the ONOS optical controller integrates with the following elements:

- The network orchestrator and the digital twin. These entities consume the REST APIs developed on top of the ONOS controller to perform requests related to service provisioning (and deletion) in the optical network. Moreover, the digital twin may retrieve from the controller detailed network topology information (e.g., per-link spectrum availability information).
- The data plane devices (e.g., transponders and ROADMs). Such devices expose to the SDN optical controller a YANG model based on OpenConfig or OpenROADM running a NETCONF server. The ONOS controller uses a NETCONF client to retrieve information and configure such devices.

Figure 12: ONOS GUI with an established intent using flexible grid.

The optical SDN controller has been tested in an emulated environment (?) and it is currently in phase of deployment in the RIGOLETTO testbeds. Fig. 12 shows three screenshots from GUI of the ONOS controller where an intent is successfully established using flex-grid along a path specified through the REST interface, alternatively the path can be computed internally. Specifically, the intent traverses all ROADMs in the network exploiting central frequency of 191.6625 THz and width 50 GHz. The figure demonstrates that: 1. the controller is able to properly setup optical intents using flex-grid; 2. the controller is able to apply routing and spectrum assignment specified using a REST APIs and therefore it can be easily integrated with a network orchestrator and a digital twin.

The SBI of the ONOS controller mainly relies on the adoption of a standardized device abstraction to ensure device compatibility and enhance vendor-neutral control plane capabilities. Three major open-source multi-vendor initiatives have been considered: OpenROADM (supported by major telecom and cloud operators), OpenConfig (supported by Google), and the Telecom Infra Project (TIP) (supported by Facebook) (20).

4.2.5 ONOS/QKD

Besides the control of optical devices, the ONOS controller has been extended for the control of QKD devices in a consistent way with the standards that are in via of definition at ETSI (21). Fig. 13 illustrates the role of the ONOS-based optical controller in a scenario where it acts as SDN controller for both the optical network and the QKD nodes.

Figure 13: Optical network architecture (including classical optical devices and QKD devices) - with representation of two relevant process flows concerning app registration (1-2) and QKD link set-up (3-6).

Regarding QKD, the ONOS controller has been extended to implement: (i) a northbound REST-based interface toward the cryptography application to enable the registration of the applications; (ii) a southbound interface based on standard ETSI 015 using NETCONF protocol for the configuration of QKD nodes; (iii) a northbound REST-based interface based on standard ETSI 018 toward the network orchestrator.

4.2.6 Mantra

The adoption of IP over Wavelength Division Multiplexing (IPoWDM) solutions has been drastically boosted by the advent of coherent pluggable transceivers. The Optical Internetworking Forum (OIF) has standardized the Common Management Interface Specification (CMIS) and extended it to digital coherent modules (DCO) through C-CMIS (Coherent CMIS), facilitating the initialization and management of optical modules.

In the Telecom Infra Project (TIP) the MANTRA (Metaverse-Ready Architectures for Open Transport) initiative has been introduced, defining hierarchical control architectures to enable the full control of IPoWDM nodes, see 14. Two main options have been proposed (i.e., Single and Dual). In both cases, the IP controller is the only element in charge of the IPoWDM nodes configuration including pluggable transceivers.

Considering the Single approach, the IP controller manages the full IPoWDM node, including the optical parameters of pluggable transceivers. The optical controller operates on the Optical Line System (OLS), controlling ROADMs and amplifiers. In the Dual architecture, the optical controller has also some read access to essential environmental data, enabling more informed decision-making.

In the context of MANTRA, the OpenConfig model has been adopted for the control of IPoWDM boxes, including packet and optical domains. The OpenConfig API has been exposed towards the SDN controller, enabling the complete configuration of the IPoWDM boxes. More specifically, for packet domain, both L2 (vlan switching) and L3 (IP routing plus BGP) are supported. For the optical domain, the pluggable configuration offers the possibility to set frequency, tx-power and application mode (by mapping it to the operational mode of the OpenConfig model).

4.2.7 Teraflow for Optical Networks

TeraFlowSDN is an open-source SDN controller based on a cloud-native and micro-service architecture developed by ETSI TeraFlowSDN (SDG TFS) (22). These microservices structure an application as a collection of interconnected and related services, using a common integration framework. In a microservices architecture, services are designed to be lightweight, modular, and highly specific, with efficient communication protocols.

Figure 14: Pluggable-based IPoWDM scenarios.

Figure 15: General architecture of TeraFlowSDN release 4 (23).

In the context of optical transport networks, TeraFlow introduces a novel Transport SDN architecture that fosters an open ecosystem for network applications and devices. It leverages fully standardized interfaces and containerized services, orchestrated on a scalable infrastructure through agile DevOps methodologies and continuous delivery workflows. Fig. 15 illustrates the general architecture of the TeraFlowSDN consisting of multiple microservices. These microservices communicate through a shared integration fabric, i.e., a framework or set of mechanisms that allow for the efficient and flexible integration of various network components and services. Release 4 includes the *Optical Controller*, allowing for lifecycle management for media channels, automated OpenConfig discovery, and efficient topology synchronization with multi-band slot representation.

The integration of TeraFlow SDN within the RESTART RIGOLETTO project is intended to function as a multi-domain controller and orchestrator, serving as an intermediary between higher-level management systems and vendor-agnostic optical network controllers.

Figure 16: TeraFlow SDN controller as a multi-domain controller.

Fig. 16 shows a scenario of using TFS as a multi-domain controller that enables inter-domain communication between local controllers that may be proprietary and/or used for different sections of the network. TeraFlow SDN will communicate with domain controllers via transport APIs while enabling privacy-preserving properties for devices in each domain, hence aligning to RESTART goals. Moreover, TeraFlow enables interoperability between different equipment vendors that often have their own proprietary controllers. The “domain” terminology used in this context may refer either to different sections of the network: (i) Access network, (ii) Metro network, and (iii) Backbone network, or it may refer to sub-domains of the same network section that are managed by different entities in case of a disaggregated optical network (24; 25). This architecture implies some communication overhead as it implies the communication via TFS between the various domain controllers. However, the main advantage lies in the fact that we can establish end-to-end connections between devices of different vendors without disclosing sensitive and proprietary information.

4.2.8 Model/ML-Based Hybrid Orchestration for Cloud-Native Network Functions

As telco networks adopt cloud-native principles, VNFs are increasingly designed using microservice architectures, enabling modularity, scalability, and agility (26). This granularity allows not only for the independent placement and scaling of entire VNFs, but also for finer-grained control of individual microservices. However, managing these microservices introduces complexities due to their inter-dependencies, resource constraints, and stringent latency requirements. The ADAPTO project has developed a framework to optimize the orchestration of computational and network resources required to deploy

5G Core Network Functions as well as third-party services to be hosted by the telco (e.g. CDNs for live streaming, IoT applications) in a cloud-edge distributed infrastructure. The ADAPTO components make the system able to dynamically adapt to fluctuating workloads and network conditions, ensuring efficient deployment and management of VNFs and microservices (27).

ADAPTO addresses some of the points previously identified in this document as future evolution areas for 3GPP work groups:

- Cross-Domain Network Slicing
- AI-Driven Closed-Loop Automation
- Cloud-Native Service Orchestration

Resource management in ADAPTO combines an SD-WAN approach for edge-to-edge orchestration of transport network resources with computational resources management in a federated cloud-edge infrastructure hosting cloud-native Network Functions and third-party services.

Transport network resources are managed by taking backhaul selection decisions at the edges of the distributed system (28).

Scaling and placement of Network Functions (NFs) are critical aspects that impact the network's performance, resource utilization, and energy efficiency. These decisions must be dynamic and adapt to changing network conditions, ensuring the efficient deployment of services and optimal use of resources.

In ADAPTO, computational resources orchestration combines dynamic service placement and migration with platform-native horizontal/vertical scaling. To this purpose, the framework uses:

- a model-based decision engine to evaluate the impact of scaling decisions based on a priori-knowledge of the system behaviour emerging from the interactions among its sub-components (29);
- a data-driven decision engine that is able to anticipate the workload evolution and exploit this knowledge to take offloading decisions that force migrations of Network Functions and other services among the sites of the distributed cloud-edge infrastructure.

Figure 17: ADAPTO hybrid approach for resource management in 5G/6G networks. $d_{O_{ijk}}(t)$: delay of k -th overlay O between site i and site j ; T_{ij} : maximum delay threshold between site i and site j ; \hat{O}_{ij} : chosen overlay between site i and site j ; $d_{\hat{O}_{ij}}$: delay on the chosen overlay; SLO: Service Level Objective on task completion time; S_m : m -th service; s_n : n -th microservice; N_i : i -th site (can be edge cloud or central cloud); $L(S_m)$: completion time for service S_m ; $R(s_n)$: allocated resources for microservice s_n .

Fig. 17 shows how these decision engines interact to optimize, at a timescale of (tens of) seconds, the use of IT resources to meet the expected Service Level Objectives.

Other opportunities that may stem from the synergy of a model-based and a data-driven approach for resource management in a distributed cloud infrastructure hosting the control and data plane of a cloud-native 5G/6G infrastructure are currently investigated in ADAPTO.

5 Future Directions Towards 6G

As network technologies evolve toward the 6G era, the complexity of network and service orchestration increases exponentially. The shift from static, domain-specific orchestration models to dynamic, cross-domain autonomous systems is imperative to meet the stringent requirements of future communication networks. The introduction of AI-driven automation, real-time decision-making, and intent-based orchestration will redefine how networks operate, ensuring enhanced scalability, efficiency, and security. Additionally, these advancements will lead to the creation of highly adaptable networks capable of responding autonomously to shifts in demand, service-level expectations, and security threats. By leveraging predictive analytics and real-time decision-making, 6G networks will dynamically configure themselves to optimize performance and ensure business continuity, even under extreme conditions. The success of 6G network orchestration will hence depend

on the ability to harmonize AI-driven intelligence, decentralized control, and real-time automation. As networks become more complex, the transition to fully autonomous orchestration will be critical to maintaining efficiency, security, and scalability. Industry collaboration will be essential in shaping open standards and interoperable frameworks to unlock the full potential of AI-driven, cross-domain network orchestration.

5.1 Architectural Evolution

The future of network orchestration requires a shift from traditional domain-specific architectures to a fully integrated cross-domain framework. The key architectural components include:

- **Hierarchical Multi-Layer Orchestration.** Combining centralized intelligence with edge-based autonomous agents to enable real-time decision-making. A distributed orchestration approach will ensure resilience, reducing bottlenecks and enhancing fault tolerance. This will enable a balance between centralized control for high-level policy enforcement and localized intelligence for real-time response, improving adaptability in ultra-dynamic network environments.
- **Service-Based Architecture (SBA) Integration.** Extending SBA principles in all domains to enable modular and composable network orchestration services. Future networks will adopt microservices-based architectures to allow seamless service chaining and dynamic workload placement. This will empower operators with fine-grained control over network services, optimizing deployments to balance efficiency and cost.
- **Cross-Domain Interoperability.** Utilizing standardized interfaces and APIs for seamless coordination across access, transport, and core networks. This will ensure holistic resource optimization and improved end-to-end service delivery, enabling multi-vendor and multi-operator environments to function cohesively. The ability to orchestrate services across different technological and administrative boundaries will be crucial for ensuring seamless, globally connected services.
- **Intent-Based Networking (IBN).** Allowing high-level service objectives to be translated into actionable network policies through AI-driven automation. Intent-based mechanisms will significantly reduce operational complexity, enabling networks to self-configure based on business and user requirements. By utilizing AI-driven decision engines, IBN will allow networks to autonomously prioritize and enforce service policies without direct human intervention.

- **Autonomous Networks.** Implementing AI-driven mechanisms that continuously analyze network conditions and autonomously adjust configurations to enhance performance and resilience. This will ensure networks proactively address congestion, interference, and failures before they impact service quality, improving efficiency and reliability.

5.2 Functional Advancements

To achieve fully autonomous orchestration, key functional improvements are required:

- **Zero-Touch Automation.** Enhancing closed-loop automation through AI/ML-driven network optimization and self-healing mechanisms. Future networks will rely on autonomous network principles to dynamically adjust configurations and manage faults. This will significantly reduce human intervention, enabling autonomous fault detection, correction, and service provisioning in real time.
- **End-to-End Network Slicing.** Enabling dynamic, on-demand allocation of network resources across multiple domains. AI-driven policies will facilitate intelligent slice management to guarantee SLAs for diverse applications, including URLLC and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). This will ensure that different network slices are efficiently allocated, maintaining performance for mission-critical applications while optimizing resource utilization.
- **Cognitive Orchestration.** Leveraging AI/ML for predictive analytics, anomaly detection, and proactive resource management. Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) techniques will allow networks to anticipate congestion and allocate resources efficiently. These predictive capabilities will allow networks to dynamically adjust to changing conditions, improving both efficiency and user experience.
- **Adaptive QoS Management.** Implementing real-time, AI-powered service assurance mechanisms to meet diverse application needs. Future orchestration will integrate digital twins to model network behavior, ensuring proactive service optimization. This will enable networks to dynamically adjust service parameters based on real-time conditions, maximizing throughput, reducing latency, and improving reliability.
- **Secure and Trustworthy Orchestration.** Integrating state of the art technologies to ensure trust, security, and compliance across federated networks. Secure enclaves and homomorphic encryption will be key to ensuring privacy-preserving orchestration. Approaches like blockchain-based would provide immutable records

of orchestration actions, enhancing transparency and reducing security risks in multi-operator environments.

- **MLOps for AI/ML Lifecycle Management.** Integrating ML Operations (MLOps) frameworks into network orchestration to ensure the continuous monitoring, validation, and retraining of AI/ML models. As AI-driven orchestration becomes more prevalent, MLOps will be critical for maintaining model accuracy, detecting concept drift, and automating the deployment of optimized models. This will enable dynamic adaptation to evolving network conditions, improving decision making and ensuring reliable service delivery. Additionally, the integration of CI/CD pipelines in MLOps will facilitate the seamless rollout of AI model updates without disrupting live network operations.

5.2.1 Key Enabling Technologies

Several enabling technologies will drive the evolution of network orchestration in 6G:

- **Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.** AI-powered decision-making for autonomous policy enforcement and predictive analytics. AI-driven orchestration agents will leverage federated learning to optimize network performance while preserving data sovereignty. These advancements will enhance the ability of networks to self-configure, detect anomalies, and respond dynamically to changes in service demand.
- **NDTs.** Simulating network behaviors and predicting service performance to enhance orchestration accuracy. NDT technology will facilitate the validation of orchestration policies before deployment, minimizing disruptions. This will enable network operators to conduct real-time network emulations, improving predictive decision-making and accelerating innovation.
- **Federated Learning.** Allowing distributed AI models to optimize network resources while preserving data privacy. Federated learning will be particularly beneficial in multi-operator environments where data sharing is restricted. By enabling AI model training across decentralized nodes without exposing raw data, federated learning will enhance security and compliance in sensitive environments.
- **Network Programmability.** Utilizing SDN, NFV, and cloud-native approaches to enhance flexibility and scalability. Future orchestration platforms will adopt intent-based APIs to dynamically control and reconfigure network slices. These pro-

programmability features will enable real-time service customization, ensuring networks can rapidly adapt to evolving business and consumer demands.

- **Quantum Computing.** Potentially accelerating complex network optimization problems in large-scale, ultra-dynamic environments. Quantum algorithms will be explored for real-time traffic routing, improving end-to-end latency and efficiency. While still in its early stages, quantum computing holds promise for solving NP-hard network optimization challenges that traditional algorithms struggle to address.
- **Edge and Fog Computing.** Enhancing localized orchestration by leveraging edge intelligence to reduce latency and improve real-time service delivery. Edge-based orchestrators will collaborate with central controllers to ensure a seamless distributed orchestration environment. This will allow critical applications, such as autonomous vehicles and smart cities, to operate with ultra-low latency and high reliability.

5.2.2 Reference Standards and Frameworks

To ensure interoperability and scalability, future network orchestration must align with evolving standards:

- **ETSI ZSM.** Defining frameworks for end-to-end automation, including cross-domain policy enforcement and real-time analytics. By providing standardized orchestration frameworks, ETSI ZSM will ensure seamless automation across diverse network environments.
- **3GPP and ITU-T 6G Standards.** Establishing guidelines for AI-driven orchestration, dynamic network slicing, and cross-domain service management. These organizations will define frameworks that ensure 6G networks are capable of advanced automation and self-optimization.
- **IETF Intent-Based Networking Standards.** Enabling high-level policy-driven orchestration with standardized intent translation mechanisms. These standards will simplify network management by ensuring that high-level business objectives are translated into real-time network configurations.
- **Open-Source Initiatives.** Leveraging frameworks like ONAP, Open RAN, and Nephio for vendor-neutral orchestration solutions. Future frameworks will integrate AI-native approaches to optimize network automation, ensuring rapid adaptability to new technological advancements.

6 Conclusions

Network and Service Orchestration is key to advanced communications and computing infrastructures, providing automation, flexibility, and scalability, and enabling not just automation and efficiency but also the delivery of intelligent and adaptive services across heterogeneous network domains. This white paper presented the design, development, and experimental validation of the next-generation orchestration platform proposed by the RESTART Grand Challenge 10 initiative. The platform follows a cloud-native, service-based architecture and introduces a modular approach to orchestration that includes domain-specific and cross-domain orchestrators, AI/ML-based intelligence, closed-loop automation, and Network Digital Twins. These components collectively enable real-time monitoring, dynamic optimization, and intent-based service delivery.

The document also provides concrete examples of how the platform functional blocks can be implemented drawing on some of the solutions developed within the RESTART project. Specifically, it introduces the following orchestration solutions, highlighting the use cases they have addressed:

- A robust Network Digital Twin framework for simulating and validating orchestration decisions in sandbox environments (COHERENT and VOLTA projects);
- A hierarchical orchestration architecture for managing services across distributed edge and cloud resources, with closed loops for service monitoring, analysis, and reconfiguration, and AI-as-a-Service for effective orchestration (WATCHEDGE project);
- An orchestration model for healthcare, leveraging predictive ML models for load and traffic forecasting and applying different QoS mechanisms across RAN, transport, and core domains (6G Salus project);
- An intelligent RAN management using O-RAN and 3GPP specifications for xApp orchestration, an LLMs-based intent-based orchestration, and intelligent orchestration of the transport network integrated in SOCCER (SUPER project);
- An optical network orchestrator and the on-going extension of ONOS for controlling optical networks and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) devices (RIGOLETTO project);
- A hybrid approach to orchestrating microservices in a cloud-edge continuum (ADAPTO project).

The document also discussed the limitations of current standardization efforts highlighting the need for stronger convergence across existing frameworks and open-source initiatives

like ONAP and Nephio. In light of this, the RESTART Grand Challenge 10 argues for a fundamental architectural shift in the orchestration of next-generation network and computing systems, from domain-specific management systems to integrated, autonomous, and cross-domain orchestration.

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